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**OBJECT DETECTION FOR LANDMARK
RECOGNITION IN SMART TOURISM APPLICATIONS**

**OBJECT DETECTION PER IL RICONOSCIMENTO DI
LANDMARK IN APPLICAZIONI DI SMART TOURISM**

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Abstract

This thesis explores the use of object detection models for monument recognition in the context of smart tourism. The goal is to develop a system capable of recognizing landmarks and monuments in images taken by tourists, providing useful information and enhancing the overall travel experience. The proposed system is evaluated on a novel dataset of Florence monuments, and the results show that the object detection model can accurately identify the landmarks in the images.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

With the advent of smart technologies, the tourism sector has experienced a significant transformation in recent years. Smart tourism applications have become increasingly effective tools for enhancing the travel experience by providing contextual and tailored information to visitors. These apps use a range of technologies, such as mobile computing, artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things (IoT).

Computer vision technologies have become more and more important in this context, as they allow applications to interpret and interact with the surrounding environment. By examining photos and videos, computer vision systems can interpret signs, identify locations and even create augmented reality experiences. Applications for smart tourism benefit greatly from this feature, which makes them more interactive and user-friendly. For example, a visitor only needs to aim his own camera at a monument to instantly receive historical details, directions and nearby points of interest from the app.

1.2 Problem Statement

In this thesis, I intend to improve the monument recognition capabilities of the *SmartTourism* application¹. The *SmartTourism* application was created as a component of a bachelor's thesis at the University of Florence and it was meant to be used as a smart tourist guide for Florence's landmarks. The app allows users to satisfy doubts and curiosities related to monuments encountered during a city visit. When a user notice a monument, he can point his own camera at it and the app, through an image retrieval system, recognizes the monument and provides supplementary information, including historical context and other pertinent details.

Its current image retrieval method, however, has some drawbacks that affect both its efficacy and user experience. The main problems concern the difficulty in recognising landmarks accurately from particular angles, with different perspectives or in difficult lighting situations. In addition, the current system has problems with recognition if only a portion of the monument is visible in the photo.

With the aim of having a more reliable and effective application, this thesis investigates the potential of the object detection approach to get beyond current limitations.

1.3 Objectives

In order to improve the *SmartTourism* application's monument recognition capabilities, I've set the following objectives:

1. Create a novel dataset for monument recognition with Florence landmarks.

¹<https://github.com/mbertini/ReInHerit-SmartTourism>

2. Create an object detection model with the new dataset.
3. Reimplement the new model in the *SmartTourism* application.

1.4 Thesis Outline

This thesis is structured to provide a comprehensive exploration of my approach to improve the *SmartTourism* application. The following chapters will explain the theoretical foundations, methodology, implementation and results of my research.

- **Chapter 2:** this chapter provides an overview of the theoretical foundations of computer vision.
- **Chapter 3:** this chapter analyzes the existing *SmartTourism* app and its limitations.
- **Chapter 4:** this chapter details my methodology to develop a new object detection system.
- **Chapter 5:** this chapter describes in detail the implementation process.
- **Chapter 6:** this chapter presents the results of the experiments and evaluations.
- **Chapter 7:** this chapter discusses the advantages, limitations, future work and suggests future research directions of this new approach.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Deep Learning for Computer Vision

Deep learning is a branch of machine learning that mimics the intricate decision-making capabilities of the human brain using multilayered neural networks called deep neural networks.

Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that uses machine learning and neural networks to teach computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital images, videos and other visual inputs.

Thanks to deep learning, computer vision has experienced a revolution: machines can now comprehend and interpret visual data with previously unheard-of accuracy and efficiency. In fact deep learning models are able to recognize patterns and features in images that are challenging to capture with conventional computer vision approaches. A deep neural network, for instance, can be trained to identify intricate patterns and characteristics at various abstraction levels, ranging from edges and textures to more abstract notions like forms and objects. [1]

Figure 2.1: Computer vision intuition

2.2 Object Detection

One computer vision technology is object detection, which locates and recognizes objects in an image. Contrary to image classification, which gives an image a single label, object detection seeks to identify several items and pinpoint each one's exact placement inside a scene (look at Figure 2.2).

The advantage of this technology is that it's able to recognize and locate objects or landmarks even when they're partially visible or obstructed. This is possible because object detection models, using techniques like region proposal networks and feature extraction, can identify and locate patterns that may correspond to specific objects, thus allowing to get an approximate

location of these object even if they're partially obscured.

Figure 2.2: Image classification vs Object detection

The main aim of this thesis is to demonstrate in fact if object detection, as opposed to image retrieval, could be a more effective method for monument recognition within the *SmartTourism* application.

Some of the most popular object detection algorithms are **Faster R-CNN**, **YOLO** (You Only Look Once), **SSD** (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) and **RetinaNet**, which differ in terms of speed, accuracy and complexity. [1] In the sections that follow, I'll examine some of the architectures mentioned above, in particular **SSD** and **RetinaNet**. The **MobileNet** technology will also be discussed, as it can play a key role in combination with object detection technologies. [2]

2.2.1 SSD: Single Shot MultiBox Detector

The Single Shot MultiBox Detector (**SSD**) is a state-of-the-art object detection algorithm known for its speed and accuracy. Unlike traditional object detection models that rely on region proposal networks, **SSD** performs detection in a single pass through a neural network, making it faster and more

efficient.

The SSD architecture consists of a base network, a set of convolutional feature maps at different scales and a set of default bounding boxes with associated confidence scores and class predictions. By predicting object classes and locations at multiple scales, SSD can detect objects of various sizes and aspect ratios in a single pass.

SSD is particularly well-suited for mobile applications due to its speed and efficiency. By eliminating the need for separate region proposal and object classification stages, SSD can achieve real-time performance on resource-constrained devices without compromising accuracy. [3]

Figure 2.3: SSD architecture

Pros:

- Because of its single pass architecture, it can make inferences faster than other detection models.
- Appropriate for real-time mobile applications, meeting the demands of smart tourism applications.

Cons:

- Less accurate when it deals with small things rather than models such as `RetinaNet`.
- Not as adaptable as pyramid-based models when managing multi-scale features.

2.2.2 RetinaNet

Using an innovative loss function called Focal Loss, the object detection model `RetinaNet` is well-known for its ability to address the problem of class imbalance in object detection.

This is especially important for datasets that may include monuments, since some landmarks could be present more frequently than others. `RetinaNet`'s multi-scale identification capability is enhanced by the use of a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN), which helps it identify objects of different sizes. [4]

Pros:

- High accuracy, especially when identifying things that are smaller or don't show up frequently in the collection.
- FPN is better at managing things of different sizes since it can effectively recognise objects on multiple scales.
- The issue of class imbalance is tackled by Focal Loss, which is helpful for identifying monuments in a tourist environment.

Cons:

- Slower than `SSD` because of its more intricate construction, which could affect performance in real time.

- More computationally expensive, but this could be offset by joint use with other models, e.g., `MobileNet` as a backbone.

2.2.3 MobileNet

`MobileNet` is a lightweight deep neural network architecture primarily designed for efficient image classification, but it can also serve as a backbone for object detection models.

Being a backbone for object detection models means:

1. Feature extraction: the backbone network processes the input image to extract important visual features.
2. Base for detection: these extracted features are then fed into the object detection-specific layers.
3. Foundational role: the backbone provides the initial representation of the image, upon which the detection model builds to identify and localize objects.
4. Replaceable component: different backbones can be swapped in or out of an object detection architecture to balance factors like speed, accuracy and model size.

Its architecture consists of depthwise separable convolutions layers followed by pointwise conv. lay. and batch normalization layers, significantly reducing model size and computational complexity while maintaining high accuracy for classification tasks.

While `MobileNet` itself is not an object detection model, it can be integrated as a backbone network in object detection architectures like `SSD` or `RetinaNet`. This integration allows these models to benefit from `MobileNet`'s

efficiency, enabling real-time performance on mobile devices with limited computational resources. [5]

Pros:

- Highly memory- and computation-efficient, which makes it ideal for mobile devices.
- Can serve as a lightweight backbone for object detection models, balancing performance and computational cost.

Cons:

- Trades off some accuracy for efficiency in classification tasks.
- When used as a backbone for object detection, it may result in slightly lower accuracy compared to heavier architectures like ResNet or EfficientNet.

2.2.4 Theoretical Considerations

From these theoretical introductions, it is clear that a combination of some of the above models would be the most appropriate solution for this project, obtaining the best from both worlds.

SSD provides faster inference, but it is less appropriate for tasks like monument recognition, where landmark sizes might vary greatly. This is due to its poorer accuracy on small objects and incapacity of multi-scale detection.

The need for a compromise between accuracy and efficiency led to the selection of RetinaNet with MobileNet as the backbone; in particular, RetinaNet was chosen for its capacity to manage class imbalance using Focal Loss, while MobileNet was chosen for its efficiency and lightweight design.

It's possible to get deeper into the architecture analysis in the Appendix B.

2.3 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a machine learning technique that uses the knowledge gained from solving a previous problem to improve the performance on a related task. In the context of deep learning, transfer learning typically involves a pre-trained model as a starting point for a new task.

This offers several advantages, including faster convergence, improved generalization and reduced data requirements. There are many scenarios in which transfer learning can be beneficial, they're all illustrated in Figure 2.4. [1]

In the context of this thesis, transfer learning plays a crucial role in developing an efficient and accurate object detection model for monument recognition. By fine-tuning a pre-trained model on a dataset of landmark images, it's possible to obtain better performances on the specific task of monument detection: the pre-trained model has already learned general features from a large dataset, which can be useful for the new task.

2.4 MediaPipe and Model Maker

MediaPipe is an open-source framework developed by Google for building multimodal machine learning pipelines. **Model Maker**, a component of **MediaPipe**, simplifies the process of creating custom machine learning models through transfer learning. [6] The models used as a starting point are pre-trained on the **COCO** dataset. [7]

Model Maker provides a user-friendly interface for fine-tuning pre-trained models on custom datasets, allowing developers to create accurate and efficient machine learning models with minimal effort. By abstracting away the complexities of model training and optimization, **Model Maker** enables rapid prototyping and deployment of machine learning solutions (Figure 2.5).

Scenario	Size of the target data	Similarity of the original and new datasets	Approach
1	Small	Similar	Pretrained network as a feature extractor
2	Large	Similar	Fine-tune through the full network
3	Small	Very different	Fine-tune from activations earlier in the network
4	Large	Very different	Fine-tune through the entire network

Figure 2.4: Transfer learning scenarios

Figure 2.5: MediaPipe Model Maker transfer learning

Chapter 3

SmartTourism: Existing System Analysis

3.1 Overview of SmartTourism

SmartTourism is a mobile application designed to enhance the tourist experience by providing real-time information about monuments and landmarks. Users can point their smartphone cameras at a monument and the app retrieves relevant historical and cultural data from a pre-loaded database.

The app was originally developed by *Lorenzo Massa* as part of his academic work. His contribution laid the foundation for the current version of SmartTourism, which incorporates various functionalities to assist users in exploring cultural sites. For more details on the initial development and design choices, please refer to Massa's work on the GitHub repository ¹.

A second version of the application ² was also developed, but the image retrieval approach went too far in the opposite direction to be reconverted,

¹Professor's fork: <https://github.com/mbertini/ReInHerit-SmartTourism>

²<https://github.com/lorenzo-massa/SmartTourism-Image-Recognition-Android>

so this new version was not considered for this project.

The main app features are:

- **Real-time Monument Recognition:** the app uses image recognition to identify monuments.
- **Cultural Information:** once recognized, the app provides users with historical facts, dates, and cultural significance of the monument.
- **Multilingual Support:** to accommodate international tourists, the app is available in multiple languages.

Despite these strengths, the existing system relies heavily on an image retrieval approach, which introduces certain performance and scalability challenges, as discussed in Section 3.3.

3.1.1 User Interface

The *SmartTourism* app features a clean and user-friendly interface, with intuitive controls for capturing images and accessing information (Figure 3.1). The main screen displays a camera viewfinder, allowing users to point their device at a monument for recognition. There's a bottom sliding menu with confidence scores about the recognitions, option for the inference and extra information about the camera settings. The app also provides a screen for extra information about the monument: it includes a preset image of the monument, an audio guide and a text description.

3.2 Image Retrieval Approach

The existing *SmartTourism* app employs an image retrieval approach for monument recognition. This technique involves capturing an image of a mon-

Figure 3.1: App Screenshots

ument, extracting its visual features, and comparing these features against a pre-existing database of monument images to find the closest match.

3.2.1 Process Flow

The image retrieval process follows several key steps:

1. Dataset Preparation:

- (a) **Preprocessing:** key images, selected to extract monuments features, undergo preprocessing, including aspect ratio preservation.
- (b) **Augmentation:** techniques such as zooming and tilting are applied to enhance the dataset.
- (c) **Feature Extraction:** features are extracted using MobileNetV3 models.

- (d) **Feature Storage:** extracted features are saved in a database for efficient retrieval.

2. Image Retrieval:

- (a) **Image Capture:** the user captures an image of the monument using the smartphone camera.
- (b) **Image Processing:** the query image undergoes the same preprocessing and augmentation as the dataset images.
- (c) **Feature Extraction:** features are extracted from the processed query image using the same MobileNetV3 model.
- (d) **FAISS Search:** the extracted features are compared with the database using FAISS for efficient similarity search.
- (e) **Post-processing:** additional processing is applied to refine the search results.
- (f) **Result Evaluation:** the retrieved results are evaluated for accuracy.
- (g) **Performance Metrics:** various metrics are used to assess the system's overall performance.

3.3 Limitations and Areas for Improvement

While the image retrieval approach has served as a functional solution for monument recognition, it presents several limitations that impact both the performance of the app and the user experience. These limitations include:

1. **Sensitivity to changes in lighting and perspective:** the system struggles to accurately recognize monuments in varying lighting conditions or from different angles. This issue is particularly evident during

night-time or low-light photography.

2. **Difficulty handling partial occlusions:** when parts of the monument are obscured by other objects (e.g., people, vehicles), the app's accuracy diminishes significantly.
3. **Limited scalability:** as the number of monuments in the database increases, the retrieval process becomes slower and less accurate, due to the growing size of the feature space.

3.3.1 Potential Improvements: Object Detection

One promising alternative to mitigate the limitations of image retrieval is the integration of object detection techniques. Unlike image retrieval, object detection can identify multiple objects within an image, even when they are partially occluded or appear under difficult angles.

Object detection models, such as those based on deep learning, have demonstrated robustness in various scenarios where traditional image retrieval approaches fail. These models could provide:

- **Better handling of occlusions:** object detection can identify visible portions of the monument, improving accuracy even in crowded scenes.
- **Real-time performance:** deep learning-based models can process images faster, ensuring smoother user interactions.
- **Scalability:** object detection models are generally more scalable, as they do not require a comparison with a large database of images.

This solves most of the above points. However, problems related to light conditions and perspective are a classic problem that can be solved with augmentation techniques.

Chapter 4

Methodology

4.1 Development Environment Setup

The development was long and multi-faceted, so it required a lot of tools. This section details the tools, libraries and workflows I employed throughout the project, highlighting their significance in achieving my objectives.

4.1.1 Tools and Libraries

- **TensorFlow:** an open-source machine learning framework, chosen for its flexibility and tools for building and training models. [8]
- **MediaPipe:** a framework for building multimodal applied machine learning pipelines, used for object detection and feature tracking. [6]
- **Albumentations:** an image augmentation library, used to expand the dataset and improve the robustness of the models. [9]
- **Git and GitHub:** a version control system (Git) and a hosting platform (GitHub) for managing code and collaboration.

- **Google Colab:** hosted Jupyter Notebook service that provides access to GPU resources, which significantly accelerated the model training. The GPUs that were used are: NVIDIA T4, NVIDIA L4 and NVIDIA A100. [10]
- **Google Drive:** cloud storage solution for datasets and model checkpoints, ensuring easy access and collaboration. Used in conjunction with *Google Colab*.
- **Android Studio:** an integrated development environment (IDE) for Android app development, used to build the mobile application and integrate the object detection model.
- **CVAT:** the Computer Vision Annotation Tool, used for manually annotating images with bounding boxes.

4.1.2 Development Workflow

The objective, as already mentioned, was to improve the *SmartTourism* app by implementing an object detection approach. In order to achieve this goal, the development workflow was structured as follows:

1. **Data Preparation:** this step involved collecting, annotating, and augmenting the datasets.
2. **Model Development:** this step focused on building and training the object detection model.
3. **App Conversion:** this step involved integrating the model into the existing SmartTourism app.
4. **Testing and Evaluation:** this step included testing the app and evaluating its performance.

Each step will be analyzed in the following sections where the methodological choices will be highlighted. In this chapter I will focus on the methodologies and design choices, while the implementation and evaluation can be found in Chapters 5 and 6 respectively.

4.2 Dataset Preparation

The primary idea was to start from an existing dataset that had some similarities with what I should have created for my project, so I started from the *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k* datasets. [11, 12] By doing this, I was able to have a better understanding of what needed to be done and a starting point to develop a training pipeline for creating a new model.

4.2.1 Oxford5k and Paris6k Datasets

Oxford5k and *Paris6k* were chosen because they were among the most famous of the monument datasets. Despite the fact that they were designed to do image retrieval, I thought it was still possible to use them for object detection, but it was necessary to perform a conversion of the annotations. The datasets info are available through these links:

- *Oxford5k*: <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/data/oxbuildings/>
- *Paris6k*: <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/data/parisbuildings/>

For the datasets and annotations download I used a GitHub repository called `revisitop`^{1 2}, a repo that contains fixed annotations and scripts to benchmark the datasets.

¹<https://github.com/filipradenovic/revisitop>

²<https://cmp.felk.cvut.cz/revisitop/>

4.2.2 Dataset Conversion (Image Retrieval to Object Detection)

To leverage the *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k* datasets for the object detection task, I needed to convert the existing annotations from an image retrieval format to bounding box coordinates suitable for object detection. So I created a series of scripts that helped me to convert the annotations: from the ground truth files (`gnd_roxford5k.pkl` and `gnd_rparis6k.pkl`) to the `.xml` files (for PASCAL VOC format) and to the `.json` file (for COCO format).

The conversion process involved several key steps:

1. **Load annotations:** the first step was to load the annotations from the ground truth files. These files contained dictionaries with information about query images, their bounding boxes and matching images categorized by difficulty (easy, hard, junk).
2. **Extract relevant information:** from the loaded data, I extracted the query bounding boxes and the list of "easy" matching images for each query. This information formed the basis for the object detection annotations.
3. **Create Bounding Box annotations:** for each query image and its corresponding "easy" matches, I created bounding box annotations. The query bounding box was used as the object of interest in these matching images.
4. **Generate XML files (PASCAL VOC):** I created individual XML files for each image containing annotations. These files included information such as the image filename, size and bounding box coordinates.
5. **Create JSON file (COCO):** in addition to the XML files, I generated a single JSON file in COCO format, which included all annotations for the

entire dataset.

All the conversion scripts are available in the GitHub repository ³ called `Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection`.

This dataset, as you can see in Section 4.3.1, allowed me to develop an important training pipeline on Mediapipe. The values I found allowed me to perform a much more efficient and fast fine-tuning process on the *Florence1k* dataset.

4.2.3 Florence1k Dataset Creation

Once I worked with *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k*, it was necessary to develop a dataset dedicated to the Florentine monuments, so I created *Florence1k* ⁴. The dataset was created by collecting images of monuments in Florence, Italy, and manually annotating them drawing bounding boxes and labeling the monuments ⁵.

It's possible to find a very detailed description of the dataset in Appendix A, here are the main features:

- Total number of images: 1200
- Number of monuments (classes): 12
- Average images per monument: 100

The dataset includes the following 12 Florentine monuments:

1. Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore (Duomo di Firenze)
2. Battistero di San Giovanni

³<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection>

⁴<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k>

⁵To address this task, I used the CVAT tool.

3. Campanile di Giotto
4. Galleria degli Uffizi
5. Loggia dei Lanzi
6. Palazzo Vecchio
7. Ponte Vecchio
8. Basilica di Santa Croce
9. Palazzo Pitti
10. Piazzale Michelangelo
11. Basilica di Santa Maria Novella
12. Basilica di San Miniato al Monte

4.2.4 Dataset Augmentation

Data augmentation is a crucial technique in deep learning that artificially expands the size and diversity of the training dataset. Given the relatively low number of dataset images, it was necessary to use augmentation techniques to ensure a more robust model and a better generalization. In order to do this, I used the `Albumentations` library.

The augmentation pipeline was designed to cover almost all possible conditions of use, in fact I applied to the images a wide range of transformations:

1. **Geometric transformations:** such as random rotations, flips and scaling to mimic different viewing angles and distances.
2. **Color augmentations:** including brightness and contrast adjustments to account for various lighting conditions.

3. **Noise injection:** to help the model become robust against image quality variations.
4. **Occlusions:** simulating partial obstruction of monuments, a common scenario in real-world applications.

In Appendix A is presented a focus for the augmentation process, there it's possible to see examples where the transformation pipeline is applied.

4.3 Model Development

The model development was handled through **Mediapipe**: first on *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k*, allowing me to develop a good training pipeline, and then on *Florence1k*, adjusting the hyperparameters and trying to improve the performances.

Transfer Learning with MediaPipe Model Maker

The benefits of using a technique such as transfer learning have already been highlighted in Section 2.3. **Mediapipe Model Maker** allowed to fine-tuning and retrain on specific datasets a pre-trained model.

To view **Mediapipe**'s documentation and solutions, simply visit the website ⁶ and search for the section that is most relevant to you.

4.3.1 Training on Oxford5k and Paris6k

As just said, the first stage of the training process involved the converted *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k* datasets. Following the guide ⁷ provided by

⁶<https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/guide>

⁷https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/customization/object_detector

Mediapipe, I was able to train the model on these datasets and I managed to achieve a decent result.

However, the training was actually conducted only on the *Paris6k* dataset. Upon reviewing the monuments in the *Oxford5k* dataset, they seemed too similar to each other, which could introduce bias into the training pipeline.

4.3.2 Fine-tuning on Florence1k

After developing a proper training pipeline with *Paris6k*, I applied it to *Florence1k*. I adjusted the newly developed strategies to improve performance results until I achieved satisfactory outcomes. The final hyperparameters and configurations are detailed in Chapter 5, while the results and evaluation are presented in Chapter 6.

4.4 App Conversion

Once the model has achieved satisfactory performance on *Florence1k* dataset, it's time to reimplement the *SmartTourism* app. The app had a precise structure: it followed a standard structure given by the `tensorflow` examples and then developed more specifically the package classification. The idea was to implement the object detection approach without distorting the essence of the app, preserving layouts, functionality and user experience. So, I went through the process of creating a new package `org.tensorflow.lite.examples.detection` and refactored the application to ensure that the new package could interact with the existing working framework without any issues. The process will be better explained in the following Chapter 5.

Chapter 5

Implementation

In this chapter I present the implementation details that were introduced in the methodology chapter. I will start by discussing the model training process, followed by the integration with the *SmartTourism* app.

5.1 Model Training Process

As mentioned in the previous chapter there were two stages of training: the first stage was training on the *Paris6k* dataset, and the second stage was fine-tuning and retraining on the *Florence1k* dataset. The training process involved the following tools:

- **Google Colab:** to run the training notebooks with GPU support.
- **Google Drive:** to store the datasets and the training notebooks.
- **Mediapipe:** to provide the object detection models.

Training on Paris6k

1. **GPU:** NVIDIA L4

2. **Dataset Preparation:** the dataset was prepared as described in the Methodology chapter (Section 4.2.1), then uploaded to `Google Drive` and mounted in the `Google Colab` environment.
3. **Model Architecture Selection:** `Mediapipe` provides 4 different object detection models: `MOBILENET_V2`, `MOBILENET_V2_I320`, `MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG` and `MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG_I384`.
I have chosen the `MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG_I384` model from the outset, as it is the most accurate model available ¹.
4. **Training Hyperparameters and Model-Specific Options:** I initially started with the default values (that can be found in the Tables B.2 and B.3), but then I moved to something more specific for the dataset. The hyperparameter on which I made more attempts was probably the `learning_rate` because `Mediapipe` does not allow to implement a real scheduler. I tried different values, including: 0.3, 0.1, 0.01 and 0.015, but in the end the most efficient one was 0.01.
The final values are:

Option	Default Value	Final Value
<code>learning_rate</code>	0.3	0.01
<code>batch_size</code>	8	64
<code>epochs</code>	30	100
<code>cosine_decay_epochs</code>	None	100
<code>cosine_decay_alpha</code>	1.0	0.1
<code>l2_weight_decay</code>	3e-5	1e-4

Table 5.1: Training Options for *Paris6k*

¹See the benchmarking results in Appendix B (Section B.6).

Some test images results are shown below:

Test 1: Defense, Paris

The inference was successful and there were two detections with confidence scores above 0.6.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 1	Class: 1
Confidence: 0.63	Confidence: 0.64

Test 2: Louvre, Paris

Even this test was successful and there were two detection that went above 0.7.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 4	Class: 4
Confidence: 0.70	Confidence: 0.72

Test 3: Pantheon, Paris

As in Test 1, there were two detections that have a confidence score higher than 0.6.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 8	Class: 8
Confidence: 0.66	Confidence: 0.67

Figure 5.1: Test Set Results for *Paris6k*

You can find the Jupyter Notebook used for training on the *Paris6k* dataset at this link ².

Training on Florence1k

1. **GPU:** NVIDIA A100
2. **Dataset Preparation:** same process as for the *Oxford5k* and *Paris6k*.
3. **Model Architecture Selection:** MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG_I384
4. **Training Hyperparameters and Model-Specific Options:** I started with the same hyperparameters found at the end of the training done with *Paris6k*, but having a more powerful GPU available, I increased the `batch_size` hoping for a better generalization.

Option	Paris6k Value	Final Value
<code>learning_rate</code>	0.01	0.01
<code>batch_size</code>	64	128
<code>epochs</code>	100	120
<code>cosine_decay_epochs</code>	100	120
<code>cosine_decay_alpha</code>	0.1	0.1
<code>l2_weight_decay</code>	1e-4	1e-4

Table 5.2: Training Options for *Florence1k*

The setup settings can be seen in Appendix B. Also, I provide a link ³ to the Jupyter Notebook used for the *Florence1k* training.

²https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection/blob/master/training/mp_training_paris6k.ipynb

³https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k/blob/master/training/mp_training_florence1k.ipynb

Here are some test images results:

Test 1: Battistero, Florence

The model successfully detected two times the monument with confidence above 0.9.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 2	Class: 2
Confidence: 0.96	Confidence: 0.98

Test 2: Santa Croce, Florence

In Test 2 the two best detections had a confidence score above 0.7.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 8	Class: 8
Confidence: 0.72	Confidence: 0.81

Test 3: Palazzo Pitti, Flor.

Another good result can be seen here. Two detection with confidence score around 0.8.

Detection 1:	Detection 2:
Class: 9	Class: 9
Confidence: 0.79	Confidence: 0.80

Figure 5.2: Test Set Results for *Florence1k*

5.2 Integration with SmartTourism App

In this section I will discuss the integration of the object detection model into the *SmartTourism* app.

This was the app structure before the integration:

Figure 5.3: App structure before detection Package integration

To incorporate the object detection functionality into the *SmartTourism* app, I made the following changes:

1. **New Package detection :**

`lib_support/`

- `Detector.java`: abstract class that defines the methods for the detection, such as `loadImage()` and `recognizeImage()`.
- `DetectorConstants.java`: class that contains static variables used in the detection process, i.e. the `LABELS` and the `DETECTION_THRESHOLDS`.
- `QuantizedDetector.java`: class that extends the `Detector` class and implements the detection methods using a quantized model.
- `StandardDetector.java`: class that extends the `Detector` class and implements the detection methods using a standard model.

`app/`

- `DetectorActivity.java`: the main activity for the object detection feature. It uses the `Detector` class to perform the detection.

2. **Asset Management:** the `tflite` model files were added to the `assets/` folder.

3. **App Refactoring:** all the necessary changes were made to the app to accommodate the new feature (e.g. all the `AndroidManifest.xml` files and the `gradle` files).

All the code related to this implementation can be found on [Github](https://github.com/eliainnocenti/ReInHerit-SmartTourism) ⁴.

⁴<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/ReInHerit-SmartTourism>

Chapter 6

Results and Evaluation

6.1 Overview on Evaluation Metrics

Object detection models are typically evaluated using two main categories of metrics: loss functions during training and COCO metrics for overall performance assessment.

Loss Functions

Loss functions measure the model's performance during training and guide the optimization process. For object detection, the total loss usually comprises:

- **Classification Loss:** measures the accuracy of class predictions for each detected object. Common implementations include cross-entropy loss or focal loss.
- **Localization (Box) Loss:** quantifies the accuracy of bounding box predictions. Often implemented as smooth L1 loss or IoU loss.
- **Objectness Loss:** in some architectures, this measures the model's confidence in detecting an object versus background.

- **Total Loss:** the weighted sum of the above components, often including additional regularization terms.

The goal during training is to minimize these losses, improving the model's ability to accurately classify objects and predict their locations.

COCO Metrics

COCO (Common Objects in Context) metrics provide a standardized way to evaluate object detection models. Key metrics include:

- **Average Precision (AP):** the primary metric, calculated over multiple Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds.
 - AP @ [0.5:0.95]: mean AP over IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 with a step of 0.05.
 - AP @ 0.50: AP at IoU threshold of 0.5 (looser criterion).
 - AP @ 0.75: AP at IoU threshold of 0.75 (stricter criterion).
- **AP across scales:**
 - AP_{small} , AP_{medium} , AP_{large} : AP for small ($area < 32^2$), medium ($32^2 < area < 96^2$) and large ($area > 96^2$) objects. These thresholds are in pixels, defining how object sizes are categorized.
- **Average Recall (AR):** The maximum recall given a fixed number of detections per image, averaged over categories and IoU thresholds.
 - AR @ 1: AR given 1 detection per image.
 - AR @ 10: AR given 10 detections per image.
 - AR @ 100: AR given 100 detections per image.
 - AR_{small} , AR_{medium} , AR_{large} : AR for objects of different scales.

These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of a model's performance,

considering various aspects such as classification accuracy, localization precision and the ability to detect objects of different sizes and in different quantities.

The combination of loss functions and COCO metrics offers a holistic view of a model’s capabilities, from training optimization to real-world performance assessment.

6.2 Model Performance on Paris6k

Some results have already been anticipated in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.1), here will be presented the results of the last training: the values of the loss functions and the COCO metrics.

The training settings are illustrated in the Table 5.1. It was performed on the *Paris6k* dataset for 100 epochs with a batch size of 64 with a NVIDIA L4 GPU (3h 26min 9s).

Training Results:

The final validation loss values are as follows:

Metric	Value
Total loss	0.7607
Classification loss	0.3564
Box loss	0.0041
Model loss	0.5629

Table 6.1: Loss functions for *Paris6k* training

The character "\" in the AP and AR tables indicates that there is an insufficient number of small and medium objects in the dataset, so that specific metric could not be calculated.

COCO Metrics:

The COCO evaluation metrics for the trained model are:

Metric				Value
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=100		0.359
AP @ IoU=0.50	area=all	maxDets=100		0.766
AP @ IoU=0.75	area=all	maxDets=100		0.278
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=small	maxDets=100		\
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=medium	maxDets=100		\
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=large	maxDets=100		0.359

Table 6.2: Average Precision (AP) for *Paris6k* training

Metric				Value
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=1		0.431
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=10		0.530
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=100		0.535
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=small	maxDets=100		\
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=medium	maxDets=100		\
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=large	maxDets=100		0.535

Table 6.3: Average Recall (AR) for *Paris6k* training

6.2.1 Analysis

The results indicate a significant challenge in precise object localization. While the model achieves a relatively high AP of 0.766 at IoU=0.50, this drops dramatically to 0.359 at IoU=0.50:0.95 and further to 0.278 at IoU=0.75. This substantial decrease in performance as the IoU threshold

increases clearly demonstrates that the model struggles with accurate object localization.

Several factors could explain these results:

1. **Annotation conversion:** the annotations were converted from image retrieval tasks, which may result in less precise bounding boxes. This could be a major contributor to the poor localization performance.
2. **Localization vs. Classification:** interestingly, despite the evident localization issues, the bounding box loss (0.0041) is much lower than the classification loss (0.3564). This discrepancy suggests that the model might be overconfident in its bounding box predictions while struggling with accurate classification.
3. **Object size bias:** the model performs consistently for large objects but lacks data for small and medium objects, indicating a potential dataset bias that could affect overall localization performance.

Future improvements should prioritize enhancing the model's ability to precisely localize objects. This could involve:

- Refining the annotation process to provide more accurate bounding boxes.
- Investigating the discrepancy between the low bounding box loss and poor localization performance.
- Diversifying the dataset to include a better balance of object sizes and more challenging localization scenarios.
- Trying different augmentation techniques to improve the model's ability to generalize across various object sizes and achieve better performance at higher IoU thresholds.

6.3 Model Performance on Florence1k

The model was retrained on the *Florence1k* dataset; the training settings are illustrated in the Table 5.2. The training was performed for 120 epochs with a batch size of 128 with a NVIDIA A100 GPU (4h 24min 12s).

Even for this dataset, some results have already been anticipated in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.2).

Training Results:

Metric	Value
Total loss	0.6264
Classification loss	0.3029
Box loss	0.0025
Model loss	0.4274

Table 6.4: Loss functions for *Florence1k* training

COCO Metrics:

Metric	Value
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=all maxDets=100	0.573
AP @ IoU=0.50 area=all maxDets=100	0.869
AP @ IoU=0.75 area=all maxDets=100	0.637
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=small maxDets=100	\
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=medium maxDets=100	0.205
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=large maxDets=100	0.577

Table 6.5: Average Precision (AP) for *Florence1k* training

Metric	Value		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=all maxDets=1	0.626		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=all maxDets=10	0.659		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=all maxDets=100	0.659		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=small maxDets=100	\		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=medium maxDets=100	0.212		
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95 area=large maxDets=100	0.663		

Table 6.6: Average Recall (AR) for *Florence1k* training

6.3.1 Analysis

The results show significant improvements compared to the *Paris6k* dataset. Here’s an analysis of the key metrics:

1. **Overall Performance:** the model shows substantial improvement on the *Florence1k* dataset compared to the *Paris6k* results. The overall AP (IoU=0.50:0.95) of 0.573 indicates good performance across various IoU thresholds.
2. **Localization Accuracy:** unlike the *Paris6k* results, the *Florence1k* model demonstrates much better localization ability:
 - The AP at IoU=0.50 (0.869) is high, indicating excellent performance at a less strict threshold.
 - The AP at IoU=0.75 (0.637) remains strong, showing that the model maintains good accuracy even with stricter overlap requirements.
 - The smaller gap between AP50 and AP75 (compared to *Paris6k*) suggests more precise bounding box predictions.

3. Object Size Performance:

- Large objects: AP of 0.577, close to the overall AP, indicating consistent performance.
- Medium objects: AP of 0.205, suggesting room for improvement in detecting medium-sized objects.
- Small objects: AP of \backslash , indicating a lack of small objects in the dataset, so the metric cannot be calculated.

4. Recall Performance: the model shows good recall metrics:

- AR for 1 detection (0.626) is high, indicating strong performance in identifying the most prominent object.
- AR for 10 and 100 detections (both 0.659) suggests the model effectively identifies multiple objects in scenes.

5. Loss Values:

- The low box loss (0.0025) corroborates the improved localization performance.
- The classification loss (0.3029) is the primary contributor to the total loss, suggesting that while localization is strong, there's still room for improvement in classification accuracy.

Comparison with Paris6k Results

The *Florence1k* model shows marked improvements over the *Paris6k* model:

- Higher overall AP (0.573 vs 0.359)
- Better localization accuracy, especially at higher IoU thresholds
- Improved performance on medium and large objects
- Higher recall across all detection limits

6.4 Comparative Analysis with Image Retrieval Model

To quantify the improvements achieved through the new approach, I conducted a comparative analysis between the two apps: the original *Smart-Tourism* app using image retrieval and the new app using object detection. In order to get better data consistency and to actually see the performance of both approaches, I used a selection of test images and I passed the bitmaps directly to the app, skipping the camera input step. The comparative analysis was performed on the monuments in common between the old implementation and the new one (same monuments as in the *Florence1k* dataset). The test monuments were: *Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore*, *Battistero di San Giovanni* and *Palazzo Vecchio*.

I made three tests to compare the two approaches:

1. **First test:** three images from the *Florence1k* dataset not used in training nor validation.
2. **Second test:** applied transformations to the images (crop and perspective) to simulate different conditions, for a total of 12 new images.
3. **Third test:** two images not containing Florentine monuments to test the model's ability to reject unrelated objects.

For each test, I recorded the top 3 predictions from both the Object Detection (OD) and Image Retrieval (IR) approaches.

First Test

The first test involved the following three images from the *Florence1k* dataset:

1. *Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore*

2. *Battistero di San Giovanni*

3. *Palazzo Vecchio*

Figure 6.1: First test images

1. florence_santamariadelfiore_0093.jpg

2. florence_battisterosangiovanni_0097.jpg

3. florence_palazzovecchio_0090.jpg

These images get through the two apps and the results are shown in the following tables ¹:

Image	1	2	3
Monument	Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore	Battistero di San Giovanni	Palazzo Vecchio
Prediction	CSFM	BSG	PV
Score 1	0.554	0.761	0.879
Score 2	0.543	0.706	0.782
Score 3	0.539	0.627	0.737

Table 6.7: Results for the first test (OD)

Image	1	2	3
Monument	Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore	Battistero di San Giovanni	Palazzo Vecchio
Prediction 1	CSFM	BSG	PV
Score 1	5.0	8.0	5.0
Prediction 2	PV	LB	CG
Score 2	11.0	10.0	11.0
Prediction 3	BSG	CSFM	CSFM
Score 3	11.0	10.0	11.0

Table 6.8: Results for the first test (IR)

¹Legend of the monuments: CSFM - Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore, CG - Campanile di Giotto, BSG - Battistero di San Giovanni, PV - Palazzo Vecchio, LB - Loggia del Bigallo.

Explaining the results:

- In Table 6.7 are shown the results for the Object Detection (OD) model. The three scores represent the three top detections per image and each score is a probability of the model's confidence in the corresponding prediction. In all cases, the correct monument was identified as the top prediction with relatively high confidence scores (ranging from 0.5 to 0.9).
- In Table 6.8 are shown the results for the Image Retrieval (IR) model. For each image, the table lists the top three predictions and their scores, which represent the three closest matches to the databases images. Here, the scores are distances: lower values indicate a closer match. The top-1 predictions were correct in all cases, but the scores suggest a certain level of uncertainty.

It is possible to conduct a more in-depth analysis of the data to identify differences, curiosities, advantages, disadvantages and other relevant insights.

- **Prediction Accuracy:** both models correctly identified the monuments in all three cases, demonstrating their effectiveness under ideal conditions.
- **Confidence Metrics:** the OD model provided clear confidence scores, with higher values indicating stronger certainty. In contrast, the IR model's distance-based scores were less intuitive, with lower values indicating closer matches.
- **Model Comparison:** while both models succeeded, they present different behaviors. The OD model, by its nature, manages to offer a list of top 3 predictions consistent with scores all belonging to the same monument. The IR model, on the other hand, produces a slightly more

ambiguous output, as it also reports matches with longer distances. However, it can often still distinguish good matches (lower scores) from worse ones (higher scores).

Since both models performed well under these controlled conditions and the difference in output format makes direct comparison challenging, this first test alone is insufficient to draw definitive conclusions about their relative strengths and weaknesses.

This leads to the second test, where I introduced a series of transformations (crop and perspective) to create more varied and realistic conditions. By applying these transformations, I created 12 new images: the aim was to assess how well each system handles variability in the data, which is crucial for real-world applications. This more rigorous evaluation will better reveal the strengths and limitations of each model when confronted with challenging scenarios.

Second Test

For the second test, I applied two types of transformations to the original images:

- **Cropped:** the images were cropped to highlight the central part of the monument, removing some surrounding context to better simulate typical user behavior.
- **Perspective:** using the `albumations` library, I applied a perspective transformation to simulate the view of the monument from a different angle, creating a more challenging scenario for the models.

1. *Cattedrale* - Cropped

1. *Cattedrale* - Perspective

2. *Battistero* - Cropped

2. *Battistero* - Perspective

3. *Palazzo Vecchio* - Cropped

3. *Palazzo Vecchio* - Perspective

Figure 6.2: Transformed versions: Cropped and Perspective

Image	1	2	3
Monument	Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore	Battistero di San Giovanni	Palazzo Vecchio
	Cropped		
Prediction	CSFM	BSG	PV
Score 1	0.603	0.766	0.858
Score 2	0.525	0.717	0.812
Score 3	0.524	0.688	0.805
	Perspective		
Prediction	CSFM	BSG	PV
Score 1	0.559	0.699	0.828
Score 2	\	0.683	0.814
Score 3	\	0.627	0.782

Table 6.9: Results for the second test (OD)

The results of the second test, as shown in Tables 6.9 and 6.10, reveal interesting insights about the performance of both models under more challenging conditions:

Object Detection (OD) Model:

- Maintained high accuracy, correctly identifying all monuments in both cropped and perspective-transformed images.
- Confidence scores remained relatively high, with most predictions above 0.5.
- Showed resilience to image transformations, with only slight decreases in confidence scores compared to the first test.

Image	1	2	3
Monument	Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore	Battistero di San Giovanni	Palazzo Vecchio
	Cropped		
Prediction 1	BSG	CSMF	PV
Score 1	8.0	8.0	6.0
Prediction 2	CSMF	BSG	CSMF
Score 2	9.0	9.0	10.0
Prediction 3	LB	CG	BSG
Score 3	10.0	11.0	12.0
	Perspective		
Prediction 1	CSMF	CSMF	PV
Score 1	4.0	6.0	6.0
Prediction 2	BSG	CG	CSMF
Score 2	10.0	11.0	11.0
Prediction 3	\	BSG	BSG
Score 3	\	11.0	11.0

Table 6.10: Results for the second test (IR)

- For the perspective-transformed image of the Cattedrale, only one detection was made, suggesting potential difficulties with severe angle changes.

Image Retrieval (IR) Model:

- Demonstrated mixed performance, with some correct top predictions but also some misclassifications.

- For cropped images, correctly identified 2 out of 3 monuments as the top prediction.
- For perspective-transformed images, correctly identified 2 out of 3 monuments as the top prediction.
- Showed more variability in its predictions, with correct answers sometimes appearing as the second prediction.
- Distance scores were generally higher (indicating less confidence) compared to the first test, reflecting the increased difficulty of the transformed images.

This test highlights the OD model's robustness to image transformations, maintaining high accuracy and confidence. The IR model, while still performing reasonably well, showed more sensitivity to these changes, with increased variability in its predictions and confidence levels.

To further evaluate the models' capabilities, I designed a third test to assess their ability to reject unrelated objects.

Third Test

For the third test, I selected two images not containing Florentine monuments. The images used were:

1. A completely black image (`black.jpg`)
2. An image of the Pantheon in Paris (`pantheon.jpg`)

The results of the third test, as presented in Table 6.11, provide valuable insights into how each model handles images unrelated to Florentine monuments:

Object Detection (OD) Model:

- Successfully avoided false positives for both unrelated images.

1. black.jpg

2. pantheon.jpg

Figure 6.3: Unrelated images used for the third test

- All confidence scores were below the threshold, indicated by \, demonstrating the model's ability to reject non-Florentine monuments.
- Showed excellent discrimination, treating both a black image and an unrelated monument (Pantheon) similarly.

Image Retrieval (IR) Model:

- Produced false positives for both unrelated images, attempting to match them to known Florentine monuments.
- For the black image, it incorrectly identified it as Palazzo Vecchio (PV) with a very low distance score of 1.0, indicating high but misplaced confidence.
- For the Pantheon image, it produced multiple predictions with varying distance scores, all incorrectly matching to Florentine monuments.
- The distance scores for the Pantheon image (7.0-11.0) were higher than

Image	black.jpg	pantheon.jpg
	Object Detection	
Prediction	\	\
Score 1	\	\
Score 2	\	\
Score 3	\	\
	Image Retrieval	
Prediction 1	PV	CG
Score 1	1.0	7.0
Prediction 2	\	CSMF
Score 2	\	10.0
Prediction 3	\	BSG
Score 3	\	11.0

Table 6.11: Results for the third test

those seen in previous tests, suggesting lower confidence, but still resulted in false positives.

This test highlights a significant advantage of the OD model in its ability to reject unrelated images, which is crucial for the reliability of a monument recognition system. The IR model's tendency to produce matches for unrelated images, sometimes with high confidence (as in the case of the black image), could lead to significant errors in practical applications.

Conclusions

It is important to preface these conclusions by acknowledging the limited sample size of this study. The tests were conducted using only three reference images (plus their transformed versions) and two additional unrelated

images. While this sample size is relatively small, it has allowed for the identification of clear trends and tendencies in the performance of both models. The following conclusions should be interpreted as preliminary findings that indicate promising directions for further research.

Based on the results of these three tests, the following conclusions can be drawn about the performance of the Object Detection (OD) and Image Retrieval (IR) approaches:

1. **Accuracy and Robustness:** despite the limited sample size, the OD model consistently demonstrated higher accuracy and robustness across all tests. It maintained high confidence in correct predictions for Florentine monuments and successfully rejected unrelated images. The IR model, while performing well in ideal conditions, showed more vulnerability to image transformations and struggled significantly with unrelated images.
2. **Handling of Transformations:** as observed in the second test, the OD model proved more resilient to image transformations such as cropping and perspective changes. It maintained high accuracy and confidence even under these challenging conditions. The IR model's performance degraded more noticeably with these transformations, sometimes misclassifying the monuments or reducing its confidence significantly.
3. **False Positive Rejection:** one of the most significant advantages of the OD model was its ability to correctly reject unrelated images, with all predictions falling below the confidence threshold. The IR model, in contrast, produced false positives for both unrelated images in the third test, which is a critical weakness for real-world applications.
4. **Confidence Interpretation:** the threshold-based approach of the OD

model offers a clear and reliable measure of the model's certainty. The distance-based scores of the IR model, while informative, led to counterintuitive results.

In conclusion, the Object Detection model demonstrates superior performance in terms of accuracy, robustness to image transformations, and particularly in its ability to reject unrelated images. These characteristics make it a more reliable choice for a monument recognition system, especially in real-world scenarios where input images may vary significantly in quality and content. The IR model's tendency to produce false positives for completely unrelated images is a significant drawback that could lead to user confusion and system unreliability.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

7.1 Summary of Contributions

This thesis provided a full reimplementation of the *SmartTourism* application, from an image retrieval approach to an object detection model for monument recognition.

The whole process, which has been described in detail in the previous chapters, is summarised in these points:

- Developing a training pipeline using the *Paris6k* dataset.
- Creating of a novel dataset with Florentine monuments (*Florence1k*).
- Creating of the new object detection model with the *Florence1k* dataset.
- Reimplementing the new object detection model within the *Smart-Tourism* app.

7.2 Implications for Smart Tourism

This work has addressed several limitations of the previous image retrieval approach, including improved accuracy in recognizing monuments and better handling of varying image conditions. The new object detection model has significantly enhanced the performance and robustness of the *SmartTourism* application; in fact, as demonstrated by the tests in Chapter 6, the new model has achieved better accuracy and robustness compared to the previous image retrieval approach.

This successful implementation of object detection for monument recognition in *SmartTourism* has broader implications for the field of Smart Tourism:

- Enhanced user experience through more accurate monument recognition.
- Technological advancements in the application of object detection models in real-world scenarios.
- Potential for wider adoption in other tourism contexts, such as city guides, museum tours, and cultural heritage applications.

Regardless of the app's context, it is interesting to note that the *Florence1k* dataset and the `tflite` model developed in this project can be valuable for research and projects beyond the scope of SmartTourism applications.

7.3 Future Directions

While this work has significantly improved *SmartTourism*, it also opens up several avenues for future research and development, including:

- **Expanding Monument Coverage:** future work could focus on including more monuments and cities, thereby enhancing the comprehensiveness and utility of the *SmartTourism* application.
- **Integration with Other Smart Tourism Technologies:** exploring potential synergies with other smart tourism technologies, such as augmented reality and personalized recommendations, could further enhance the user experience and application capabilities.
- **Addressing Remaining Challenges:** identifying and addressing any remaining limitations, such as improving the detection of small objects and reducing model size for deployment on resource-constrained platforms, will be crucial for future advancements.

Appendix A

Dataset Florence1k

A.1 Dataset Overview

Florence1k is a novel dataset created for monument recognition in Florence, Italy. The dataset is designed for both object detection and image retrieval tasks, featuring the following key characteristics (Latest update: September 2024):

- Total number of images: 1200
- Number of monuments (classes): 12
- Average images per monument: 100
- Image resolution: variable, with a minimum dimension of 50000 pixels (width x height)
- Average annotations per image: 1.49 (for object detection)

The dataset is publicly available and everything is stored in a GitHub repository¹, which contains all necessary files, annotations and documentation.

¹<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k>

A.2 Monument Classes

The dataset includes the following 12 Florentine monuments:

1. Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore (Duomo di Firenze)
2. Battistero di San Giovanni
3. Campanile di Giotto
4. Galleria degli Uffizi
5. Loggia dei Lanzi
6. Palazzo Vecchio
7. Ponte Vecchio
8. Basilica di Santa Croce
9. Palazzo Pitti
10. Piazzale Michelangelo
11. Basilica di Santa Maria Novella
12. Basilica di San Miniato al Monte

Figure A.1: Representative images of the 12 Florence monuments (Part 1)

Figure A.2: Representative images of the 12 Florence monuments (Part 2)

A.3 Dataset Structure

The dataset is organized in the following structure:

Figure A.3: Structure of the *Florence1k* dataset

A.4 Image Details

A.4.1 Image Sources

The images used in this dataset are primarily sourced from user uploads on Google Maps and Google Images. These images were taken around Florence by tourists and locals and depict the monuments listed in Section A.2.

The URLs of the images are provided in a CSV file² included in the dataset repository.

²<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k/blob/master/images/images.csv>

A.4.2 Image Format

- All images are in JPEG format.
- Images are in RGB color space.
- Resolution varies, but all images have a minimum dimension of 50000 pixels (width x height).

A.4.3 Image Content

The dataset includes a diverse range of images for each monument:

- Different angles and perspectives
- Various lighting conditions (day, night, sunny, cloudy)
- Different seasons
- With and without crowds
- Close-ups and distant views

Figure A.4: Example images of the Cattedrale di Santa Maria del Fiore

A.4.4 File Naming Convention

Images are named using the following convention:

```
florence_<monument_name>_<image_id>.jpg
```

For example:

- florence_santamariadelfiore_0097.jpg
- florence_pontevectchio_0052.jpg

A.5 Object Detection

For object detection tasks, annotations are provided in both PASCAL VOC and COCO formats. Additionally, a model has been created using the *Florence1k* dataset.

A.5.1 Data Preparation

Augmentation

To increase the dataset size and improve model generalization, data augmentation techniques were applied to the images. Augmentation was performed on the training set using the `augmentations` library³, with the following transformations:

- Random Resized Crop
- Horizontal Flip
- Random Brightness/Contrast
- Hue/Saturation/Value adjustment
- Gaussian Noise

³<https://augmentations.ai/docs/>

- Random Shadow
- CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization)
- Motion/Median/Gaussian Blur
- Shift/Scale/Rotate

It is possible to look at the code snippet for the data augmentation pipeline in Appendix C.

Original image

Augmentation 1

Augmentation 2

Augmentation 3

Figure A.5: Augmentation examples for Palazzo Vecchio

Figure A.6: Augmentation examples for Campanile di Giotto

Dataset Split

The dataset was divided into three subsets:

- Training set: 60% (720 images)
- Validation set: 30% (360 images)
- Test set: 10% (120 images)

The split was performed ensuring that each monument class was proportionally represented in each subset.

The dataset was augmented to increase the number of images for training.

For each image in the training set, four augmented versions were generated, resulting in a 5x increase in the size of the training set.

After augmentation, the sets contain the following number of images:

- Training set: 3600 images
- Validation set: 360 images

Figure A.7: Dataset split before and after augmentation

A.5.2 Training

This dataset was made for this project and was used to train an object detection model in order to recognize the monuments in Florence. The model was trained using the `MediaPipe Model Maker` library, which provides an easy-to-use interface for training object detection models on custom datasets.

It's possible to get deeper into the model training process by checking the code snippet for setting up and training the model in Appendix C. Instead, if you want to know more about the model architecture and hyperparameters, you can check the next appendix.

Here are some details about the training process:

- Model architecture: `MobileNetV3 Large`
- Configuration: `MobileNet MultiHW AVG I384`

- Input size: 384x384
- Hyperparameters:
 - Learning rate: 0.01
 - Batch size: 128
 - Number of epochs: 120
 - Cosine decay epochs: 120
 - Cosine decay alpha: 0.1
 - L2 weight decay: 1e-4
- Data augmentation: as described in the previous section
- GPU: NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB
- Training time: 4 hours and 25 minutes on a single GPU

A.5.3 Performance

The model, based on the MobileNetV3 Large architecture, achieved the following results. A thorough analysis and discussion of these outcomes can be found in Section 6.3.

Metric	Value
Total loss	0.6264
Classification loss	0.3029
Box loss	0.0025
Model loss	0.4274

Table A.1: Loss functions

Metric				Value
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=100		0.573
AP @ IoU=0.50	area=all	maxDets=100		0.869
AP @ IoU=0.75	area=all	maxDets=100		0.637
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=small	maxDets=100		\
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=medium	maxDets=100		0.205
AP @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=large	maxDets=100		0.577

Table A.2: Average Precision (AP)

Metric				Value
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=1		0.626
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=10		0.659
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=all	maxDets=100		0.659
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=small	maxDets=100		\
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=medium	maxDets=100		0.212
AR @ IoU=0.50:0.95	area=large	maxDets=100		0.663

Table A.3: Average Recall (AR)

Metric	Value	Metric	Value
AP	0.57329375	ARmax1	0.6258163
AP50	0.8686483	ARmax10	0.6588841
AP75	0.63735133	ARmax100	0.65906525
APs	\	ARs	\
APm	0.20470297	ARm	0.2125
APl	0.5765207	ARl	0.6627668

Table A.4: COCO Metrics Summary

Figure A.8: Training and validation loss over epochs

Figure A.9: COCO Metrics

Figure A.10: Average Precision and Average Recall

A.6 Image Retrieval

Although the dataset was initially designed for object detection, it can also be used for image retrieval tasks. This is possible because the dataset still contains a good variety of images, but it is important to set a series of steps that allows to convert the annotations originally intended for object detection into annotations suitable for image retrieval tasks.

The idea is to create a `florence1k.pkl` file that contains the essential data required for the image retrieval task. This includes:

1. **gnd**: a dictionary that stores the ground truth information for each query image. This typically includes:

- **Query bounding box**: the specific area of interest in the query image that should be used for the retrieval process.
- **Matching images**: a dictionary with confidence levels, such as "easy", "hard", and "junk". These indicate different levels of difficulty in matching images from the dataset to the query image.

For example:

- **Easy**: images that are very similar to the query image and should be retrieved with high confidence.
- **Hard**: images that are somewhat similar but present more variation, making them more challenging to retrieve.
- **Junk**: images that are either irrelevant or very different from the query image, which should ideally not be retrieved.

2. **imlist**: a comprehensive list of all the images available in the dataset.

These are the images that will be compared to the query images during the retrieval process. The system will search through this list to find

the most relevant matches based on the query bounding boxes and the ground truth data.

3. **qimlist:** this is the list of query images, each of which has a corresponding bounding box in the gnd dictionary. These query images serve as the inputs for the retrieval system. The system will aim to retrieve similar images from the dataset based on the content within the query bounding box.

By organizing the dataset in this way, the retrieval task becomes well-defined, with clear ground truth annotations that allow for accurate evaluation of the system’s performance. The `florence1k.pkl` file will thus serve as the foundational structure for managing the query images, the dataset and the relevant annotations, ensuring that the image retrieval model can operate efficiently and effectively.

Here is a step-by-step guide to convert object detection annotations into annotations suitable for an image retrieval dataset, similar to what is structured in the `.pkl` file:

1. **Select Query Images:** choose one or more query images per monument that capture diverse viewpoints and conditions.
2. **Extract Bounding Boxes:** use the existing bounding boxes from object detection annotations (e.g., COCO, Pascal VOC) to define the region of interest for each query image.
3. **Compare Bounding Boxes:** for each query, compare its bounding box with objects in the other dataset images using metrics like IoU or visual similarity (e.g., feature embeddings).
4. **Set a Similarity Metric:** define a metric (e.g., IoU or embedding distance) to classify the level of similarity between the query bounding

box and the dataset images.

5. **Classify Images into Confidence Levels:** group dataset images based on their similarity to the query image:
 - **Easy:** high similarity in both content and bounding box.
 - **Hard:** the same object but with variations (viewpoint, occlusion).
 - **Junk:** irrelevant or poor-quality images.
6. **Build Ground Truth:** for each query, create a dictionary with the bounding box and lists of images grouped by confidence levels (easy, hard, junk).
7. **Finalize the Dataset:** organize the query images, bounding boxes, and confidence levels into a structured format like `.pkl`.

These steps outline how the dataset could be adapted for retrieval tasks without requiring significant modifications. However, it is important to note that this functionality has not yet been implemented. Future work could involve developing a system that retrieves similar images of the monuments and highlights the specific regions of interest (as defined by the bounding boxes) within those images, enhancing the precision and relevance of retrieval results.

In summary, while the dataset’s current setup is primarily focused on object detection, its potential for image retrieval—especially for identifying specific monuments—is significant, and the necessary steps for this adaptation have been identified, awaiting future implementation.

A.7 Usage Rights

This section outlines the considerations related to the usage of images. While these images are sourced from public uploads, it's important to note:

- The images are used exclusively for research and educational purposes, in accordance with fair use principles.
- For any commercial use of this dataset, it is essential to obtain the necessary permissions.
- No ownership of the images is claimed; all rights remain with the respective owners.

Ethical Considerations

Special attention has been given to ensure that the dataset:

- Does not contain any inappropriate or offensive content
- Does not include identifiable individuals
- Does not violate any privacy or copyright laws
- Represents a diverse range of perspectives and conditions

In case any images raise ethical concerns, it is recommended to contact the dataset maintainers ⁴ for further action.

⁴Elia Innocenti - elia.innocenti@edu.unifi.it

Appendix B

Model Architecture Details

B.1 Introduction

This appendix provides an analysis of the object detection model designed for the *Florence1k* dataset using `MediaPipe`. This detailed breakdown covers the model's architecture, training configuration, performance metrics and potential areas for future improvement.

B.2 Model Architecture Overview

The object detection model is based on the `MobileNetV3` architecture, which offers a good balance between performance and computational efficiency. The key specifications are:

- Model architecture: `MobileNetV3 Large`
- Configuration: `MobileNet MultiHW AVG I384`
- Input size: `384x384`

B.3 Model Components and Structure

The model's architecture is made up of multiple key parts, each of which has a specific function in the detection process:

- **MobileNet Backbone:** a modified version of MobileNetV3 used for efficient feature extraction across different scales.
- **Feature Pyramid Network (FPN):** this component is responsible for aggregating multi-scale features, which is essential for detecting objects of various sizes.
- **RetinaNet Head:** this head is responsible for bounding box regression and object classification.
- **Multilevel Detection Generator:** this module generates the final set of detections by integrating the outputs from different levels.

The model's architecture is summarized in the following table:

Model: "retina_net_model"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
mobile_net (MobileNet)	{'2': (None, 96, 96, 32), '3': (None, 48, 48, 64), '4': (None, 24, 24, 160), '5': (None, 12, 12, 192), '6': (None, 1, 1, 1280)}	3704416
fpn (FPN)	{'5': (None, 12, 12, 128), '4': (None, 24, 24, 128),	144928

```

'3': (None, 48, 48, 128),
'6': (None, 6, 6, 128),
'7': (None, 3, 3, 128)}

multilevel_detection_generator (MultilevelDetectionGenerator) multiple 0

retina_net_head (RetinaNet Head) ({'3': (None, 48, 48, 117), 183833
'4': (None, 24, 24, 117),
'5': (None, 12, 12, 117),
'6': (None, 6, 6, 117),
'7': (None, 3, 3, 117)},
{'3': (None, 48, 48, 36),
'4': (None, 24, 24, 36),
'5': (None, 12, 12, 36),
'6': (None, 6, 6, 36),
'7': (None, 3, 3, 36)},
{ })

=====
Total params: 4,033,177 (15.39 MB)
Trainable params: 3,985,113 (15.20 MB)
Non-trainable params: 48,064 (187.75 KB)

```

Listing 1: Model Architecture Summary

It's possible to see the model architecture with Netron by the following link: Netron Model Viewer ¹.

¹<https://netron.app/?url=https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k/blob/master/models/model.tflite>

B.3.1 Input and Output Specifications

The input to the model is an image with a resolution of 384x384 pixels. The image is preprocessed to normalize pixel values to the range [0,1]. The output of the model consists of two main components:

- **Bounding Box Predictions:** a set of bounding boxes indicating the location of detected objects within the image. Each bounding box is represented by four coordinates (x,y,width,height).

Tensor *detection_boxes* :

$$[\text{batch}, \text{num_detections}, \text{box_coords}] \rightarrow [1, 27621, 4]$$

- **Class Predictions:** a set of class scores for each bounding box, indicating the probability of the object belonging to each class.

Tensor *detection_scores* :

$$[\text{batch}, \text{num_detections}, \text{class_scores}] \rightarrow [1, 27621, 13]^2$$

B.4 Training Setup and Hyperparameters

These tables provide a comprehensive overview of the configurable elements in the object detection model training process using `MediaPipe Model Maker`. By adjusting these parameters, it's possible to fine-tune the model to best suit a specific use case with specific dataset characteristics.

The code snippet for setting up and training the model can be found in Appendix C.

The choice of hyperparameters, such as `learning rate` and `batch size`, can significantly impact model convergence and generalization. It may take

²13 classes: 12 monuments + background

more attempts and experiments before you can find the values that optimize performance.

`MediaPipe Model Maker` offers the possibility to quantize the model to reduce its size and improve inference speed on edge devices. The project opted for the classical approach using the `float32` model instead of the quantized version. This decision was taken to maintain greater simplicity in implementation. Nothing prevents the continued development of a quantized version and subsequent comparison of speed and accuracy.

B.4.1 Model Architecture Selection

The choice of model architecture is fundamental to the training process. `MediaPipe Model Maker` supports several pre-defined architectures, each with its own characteristics:

Supported Model	Description
<code>MOBILENET_V2</code>	Standard <code>MobileNetV2</code> architecture
<code>MOBILENET_V2_I320</code>	<code>MobileNetV2</code> with 320x320 input resolution
<code>MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG</code>	<code>MobileNet</code> with multi-scale feature fusion and average pooling
<code>MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG_I384</code>	<code>MobileNet</code> with multi-scale feature fusion, average pooling, and 384x384 input resolution

Table B.1: Supported Model Architectures

B.4.2 Training Hyperparameters

The `HParams` class allows for the customization of various training-related parameters:

Option	Default Value	Description
<code>learning_rate</code>	0.3	Learning rate for gradient descent training
<code>batch_size</code>	8	Batch size for training
<code>epochs</code>	30	Number of training iterations over the dataset
<code>cosine_decay_epochs</code>	None	Number of epochs for cosine decay learning rate (if <code>None</code> , set to <code>epochs</code>)
<code>cosine_decay_alpha</code>	1.0	Alpha value for cosine decay learning rate

Table B.2: Training Hyperparameters

B.4.3 Model-Specific Options

The `ModelOptions` class provides control over model-specific parameters:

Option	Default Value	Description
<code>l2_weight_decay</code>	3e-5	L2 regularization penalty

Table B.3: Model-Specific Options

B.4.4 Quantization-Aware Training Parameters

For models undergoing Quantization-Aware Training (QAT), the `QATParams` class offers additional customization:

Option	Default Value	Description
<code>learning_rate</code>	0.3	Learning rate for QAT
<code>batch_size</code>	8	Batch size for QAT
<code>epochs</code>	15	Number of QAT iterations
<code>decay_steps</code>	8	Learning rate decay steps for Exponential Decay
<code>decay_rate</code>	0.96	Learning rate decay rate for Exponential Decay

Table B.4: Quantization-Aware Training Parameters

B.5 Evaluation and Performance Metrics

Evaluating the performance of an object detection model is crucial for understanding its effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement. This section discusses the key metrics used to assess the model’s performance, with a particular focus on the COCO (Common Objects in Context) evaluation metrics.

B.5.1 Model Evaluation Process

After training the model, it is evaluated on a separate validation dataset to assess its generalization capabilities. The evaluation process typically involves the following steps:

1. Running the model on the validation dataset.
2. Computing the loss function.
3. Calculating various performance metrics, particularly the COCO metrics.

The evaluation can be performed using the code snippet in Appendix C.

B.5.2 Key Performance Metrics

Loss Function

The loss function quantifies the difference between the model's predictions and the ground truth. A lower loss value generally indicates better model performance. However, the loss alone is not sufficient to fully assess the model's capabilities in object detection tasks.

COCO Metrics

The COCO metrics provide a comprehensive set of measures for evaluating object detection models. The most important of these is the Average Precision (AP), which balances both the precision and recall of the model across different confidence thresholds and object sizes.

Key COCO metrics include:

- **Average Precision (AP)**: this is the primary metric for evaluating object detection models. It is calculated by taking the mean precision over a range of recall values (0 to 1) and over all object categories.
- **AP @ .50 (AP at IoU = .50)**: this metric calculates the AP with a minimum Intersection over Union (IoU) of 0.5 between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes.

- **AP @ .75** (AP at IoU = .75): similar to AP @ .50, but with a stricter IoU threshold of 0.75.
- AP_{small} , AP_{medium} , AP_{large} : these metrics evaluate AP for small, medium, and large objects respectively, providing insights into the model’s performance across different object sizes.
- **Average Recall AR**: this metric represents the maximum recall given a fixed number of detections per image, averaged over all categories and IoU thresholds.

B.6 Benchmarking

This section presents benchmarking results for the supported model architectures, as reported by `MediaPipe`. These models were trained and evaluated on the android figurines dataset, which is the same dataset used in the `MediaPipe Model Maker` notebook. It’s important to note that this information is sourced directly from the `MediaPipe` documentation and reflects their internal testing.

Before examining the benchmarking results, several key points should be considered:

- The android figurines dataset is small and relatively simple, consisting of only 62 training examples and 10 validation examples. Due to the limited size of the dataset, metrics may exhibit significant variance across different training runs.
- This dataset was provided primarily for demonstration purposes. For production-grade models, it is strongly recommended to collect a larger and more diverse set of data samples.

- The float32 models were trained using the default HParams, while the int8 models underwent Quantization-Aware Training (QAT) with specific parameters: `QATHParams(learning_rate=0.1, batch_size=4, epochs=30, decay_rate=1)`.
- When working with custom datasets, it may be necessary to fine-tune both HParams and QATHParams to achieve optimal results. Refer to the Hyperparameters section for more information on configuring these training parameters.
- All latency measurements were benchmarked on a Pixel 6 device.

The following table summarizes the benchmarking results for various model architectures:

Model Architecture	Input Image Size	Test AP	
		float32	QAT int8
MobileNetV2	256x256	88.4%	73.5%
MobileNetV2 I320	320x320	89.1%	75.5%
MobileNet MultiHW AVG	256x256	88.5%	70.0%
MobileNet MultiHW AVG I384	384x384	92.7%	73.4%

Table B.5: Benchmarking Results: Input Size and Test AP

These benchmarking results provide valuable insights into the trade-offs between model accuracy, latency, and size across different architectures and quantization levels. They can serve as a reference point when selecting an appropriate model for specific application requirements, balancing factors such as detection accuracy, inference speed, and memory constraints.

It's crucial to remember that these results are specific to the android figurines dataset and may not directly translate to performance on other

Model Architecture	CPU Latency		Model Size	
	float32	QAT int8	float32	QAT int8
V2	48ms	16ms	11MB	3.2MB
V2 I320	75ms	33.38ms	10MB	3.3MB
MultiHW AVG	56ms	19ms	13MB	3.6MB
MultiHW AVG I384	238ms	41ms	13MB	3.6MB

Table B.6: Benchmarking Results: CPU Latency and Model Size

datasets or in different application contexts. When developing models for production use, it's advisable to conduct thorough benchmarking on your specific dataset and target hardware to ensure optimal performance.

Appendix C

Code Snippets

C.1 Overview

This appendix provides key code snippets used in the development of the *Florence1k* dataset and the associated object detection model.

For the full codebase, refer to the GitHub repository at:

- [eliainnocenti/Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection](https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection) ¹
- [eliainnocenti/Florence1k](https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k) ²
- [eliainnocenti/ReInHerit-SmartTourism](https://github.com/eliainnocenti/ReInHerit-SmartTourism) ³

The principal code snippets included in this appendix are related to:

- Data Augmentation
- Model Training
- Evaluation Metrics

¹<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Oxford5k-Paris6k-ObjectDetection>

²<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/Florence1k>

³<https://github.com/eliainnocenti/ReInHerit-SmartTourism>

C.2 Data Augmentation

The following code snippet shows the data augmentation pipeline used:

```
import albumentations as A

bboxes_params = A.BboxParams(format='coco', min_visibility=0.3,
    ↪ label_fields=['class_labels'])

transform = A.Compose([
    A.RandomResizedCrop(height=640, width=640, scale=(0.8, 1.0),
    ↪ ratio=(0.9, 1.1), p=0.3),
    A.HorizontalFlip(p=0.5),
    A.RandomBrightnessContrast(brightness_limit=0.2,
    ↪ contrast_limit=0.2, p=0.5),
    A.HueSaturationValue(hue_shift_limit=20, sat_shift_limit=30,
    ↪ val_shift_limit=20, p=0.5),
    A.GaussNoise(var_limit=(10.0, 50.0), p=0.5),
    A.RandomShadow(num_shadows_lower=1, num_shadows_upper=3,
    ↪ shadow_dimension=5, shadow_roi=(0, 0.5, 1, 1), p=0.3),
    A.CLAHE(clip_limit=4.0, tile_grid_size=(8, 8), p=0.5),
    A.OneOf([
        A.MotionBlur(blur_limit=7, p=0.5),
        A.MedianBlur(blur_limit=7, p=0.5),
        A.GaussianBlur(blur_limit=7, p=0.5),
    ], p=0.3),
    A.ShiftScaleRotate(shift_limit=0.1, scale_limit=0.2,
    ↪ rotate_limit=15, border_mode=0, p=0.5)
], bbox_params=bboxes_params)
```

Listing 2: Data Augmentation Pipeline

C.3 Model Training

C.3.1 MediaPipe Object detection model customization

It's possible to refer to the official Template given by MediaPipe, that can be found on GitHub ⁴ or on the official website ⁵.

C.3.2 Fine-tuning on Florence1k Dataset

The code for setting up and training the model:

```
spec = object_detector.SupportedModels.MOBILENET_MULTI_AVG_I384

hparams = object_detector.HParams(
    learning_rate=0.01,
    batch_size=128,
    epochs=120,
    cosine_decay_epochs=120,
    cosine_decay_alpha=0.1,
    shuffle=True,
    export_dir='exported_model'
)

model_options = object_detector.ModelOptions(
    l2_weight_decay=1e-4
)

options = object_detector.ObjectDetectorOptions(
    supported_model=spec,
```

⁴https://github.com/google-ai-edge/mediapipe-samples/blob/main/examples/customization/object_detector.ipynb

⁵https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/customization/object_detector

```

        hparams=hparams,
        model_options=model_options
    )

    model = object_detector.ObjectDetector.create(
        train_data=train_data,
        validation_data=validation_data,
        options=options
    )

```

Listing 3: Model Training Setup

C.4 Evaluation Metrics

```

loss, coco_metrics = model.evaluate(validation_data, batch_size=4)
print(f"Validation loss: {loss}")
print(f"Validation coco metrics: {coco_metrics}")

```

Listing 4: Evaluation Metrics

```

3/3 [=====] - 9s 2s/step - total_loss:
↪ 0.6264 - cls_loss: 0.3029 - box_loss: 0.0025 - model_loss:
↪ 0.4274

Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.573

Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50 | area= all |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.869

Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.75 | area= all |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.637

Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = -1.000

Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.205

```

```
Average Precision (AP) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.577
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all |
↪ maxDets= 1 ] = 0.626
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all |
↪ maxDets= 10 ] = 0.659
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= all |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.659
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= small |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = -1.000
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area=medium |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.212
Average Recall (AR) @[ IoU=0.50:0.95 | area= large |
↪ maxDets=100 ] = 0.663
Validation loss: [0.6264222264289856, 0.3028503954410553,
↪ 0.0024915586691349745, 0.42742833495140076]
Validation coco metrics: {'AP': 0.57329375, 'AP50': 0.8686483,
↪ 'AP75': 0.63735133, 'APs': -1.0, 'APm': 0.20470297, 'APl':
↪ 0.5765207, 'ARmax1': 0.6258163, 'ARmax10': 0.6588841,
↪ 'ARmax100': 0.65906525, 'ARs': -1.0, 'ARm': 0.2125, 'ARl':
↪ 0.6627668}
```

Listing 5: Evaluation Metrics Output

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